

Advantages and Disadvantages of Utilizing Markov Chains in a Digital Marketing Strategy to Predict E-Commerce Sales

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Abstract

This study analyzes competition among three major e-commerce platforms in Indonesia - Shopee, Lazada, and Tokopedia - using the Markov Chain model. The primary focus is to evaluate the marketing mix, including price, promotion, security, service, and product availability, within the Mataram City e-commerce market. Data on consumer use of these platforms are analyzed to predict market share and consumer behavior over time. The findings demonstrate how the Markov Chain model can predict shifts in market share among these platforms and provide insights into the future effectiveness of their marketing strategies. This model enables companies to optimize promotional costs and refine marketing approaches, preparing them to compete in an increasingly competitive market.

Keywords: *Markov chain model, e-commerce, marketing mix.*

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Introduction

Digitalization in marketing has become essential for reaching, engaging, and retaining today's technology-driven customers. Beyond technology, digitalization is also driven by evolving consumer behavior and an increasingly dynamic business environment. With the widespread use of smartphones, consumers are constantly connected, and many interactions - ranging from shopping to socializing - have shifted online. Social media platforms now serve as major source of influence, where individuals follow brands, influencers, and trends that shape their purchasing decisions.

Digital channels generate vast amounts of data on consumer behavior, preferences, and buying patterns, providing invaluable insights into consumer needs. Digitalization enables marketers to create targeted, personalized campaigns by tailoring content for specific customer segments, thereby increasing engagement and conversion rates. Moreover, digital channels allow companies to monitor campaigns in real time, enabling immediate adjustments to optimizing marketing strategies. Compared to traditional media like TV, radio, and newspapers, digital marketing channels such as social media, email, and SEO are often more cost-effective. Precise targeting in

digital marketing typically results in higher returns by reaching the right audience with minimal waste, a significant improvement over traditional methods.

To stay relevant and competitive, companies need to maintain a strong online presence. Digital marketing allows brands to be agile, respond swiftly to consumer trends and feedback, and adapt messaging or products based on current market demands. The integration of technologies such as automation tools and artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming digital marketing, enabling companies to automate repetitive tasks and deliver more personalized experiences. New digital marketing technologies offer immersive experiences - such as interactive ads and virtual try-ons - that enhance customer engagement. Additionally, digital platforms allow brands to build communities around their products, fostering increased loyalty and encouraging word-of-mouth promotion.

A Markov Chain is a mathematical model that predicts the probability of transitioning from one state to another in a sequence. In digital marketing, Markov Chains are particularly useful for understanding and predicting customer behavior as consumers move through various stages of the marketing funnel. Customers engage with brands across multiple channels (e.g., social media, email, websites, ads), and Markov Chains help identify the paths customers take before making a purchase, allowing marketers to determine which touchpoints are most effective.

Markov Chains assign credit to each touchpoint based on the likelihood that it contributed to the final conversion, offering a more accurate view of each channel's contribution. Unlike simple models such as first-touch or last-touch attribution, Markov Chains predict the likelihood of a customer moving between stages (e.g., from engaged to inactive or from browsing to buying). This enables marketers to identify customers at risk of churn who may benefit from targeted retention efforts. By analyzing actions that lead to either churn or retention, brands can develop strategies to keep customers engaged. For instance, if a customer shifts from active to disengaged, a timely email or message could help re-engage them.

Markov Chains also aid marketers in determining the likelihood of a user advancing through a particular stage after seeing an ad, allowing for optimized budget allocation on channels and campaigns most likely to convert. By modeling users' transitions through ads and content, marketers can evaluate which campaigns yield desired results, leading to more efficient and cost-effective strategies. Furthermore, analyzing customer paths allows marketers to create segments based on the probability of users moving between stages, categorizing customers by behavior rather than traditional demographics. These insights enable marketers to personalize messaging, targeting likely converters with promotions and loyalty-building offers to those less likely to engage.

Markov Chains enable marketers to identify stages with high churn rates, allowing for targeted interventions. Once high-churn stages are identified, marketers can experiment with strategies to mitigate churn. By analyzing the most common transition paths, companies can design improved user experiences and optimize calls to action, making it easier for customers to progress through each stage. Markov Chains also assist in designing and analyzing tests, as they allow marketers to measure the impact of changes on the likelihood of users advancing from one stage to another. Observing changes in transition probabilities enables marketers to continuously test and refine various aspects of their campaigns, ultimately enhancing overall performance.

Literature Review

A Markov Chain is a mathematical model that describes a system that transitions from one state to another based on probability. In this model, the future state depends only on the current state and

not on the history of previous states. Markov Chains are often used in the analysis of complex systems and assist in decision-making based on patterns that emerge from these transitions.

Markov Chains in marketing economics are a powerful tool for understanding and predicting consumer behavior. By modeling transitions between stages in the buying process, companies can develop more effective marketing strategies and enhance conversion rates.

Markov Chains are superior to other models, such as logistic regression, decision trees, or data mining models, in consumer behavior analysis due to their ability to model sequential transitions, flexible probabilistic approach, memoryless property, ease of transition matrix construction, optimization of resource allocation, and dynamic evaluation of campaign effectiveness.

Ability to Model Sequential Transitions

Markov Chains are specifically designed to analyze systems that rely on a sequence of transitions from one state to another, which is particularly relevant for understanding the consumer journey. In the purchasing process, consumers often progress through sequential stages (e.g., awareness → interest → consideration → purchase). Logistic regression and decision tree models typically do not consider this sequence of stages, focusing more on the static relationships between variables.

Flexible Probability Approach

Markov Chains measure the probability of moving between stages (or “transitions”), allowing marketers to predict the likelihood of consumers advancing from one stage to the next. This enables marketers to identify critical points or stages with high churn rates. By contrast, other models such as logistic regression are more commonly used for binary prediction or static estimation and do not focus on gradual transitions between stages in the buying cycle.

Memoryless Property.

Markov Chains have a memoryless property, where the decision to move to the next state depends only on the current state and not on previous history. This property makes Markov Chains more efficient for models that emphasize current-state-based transitions, such as consumer switching patterns. Other data mining models often require more complex historical data to predict future behavior.

Ease of Transition Matrix Construction

Markov Chains allow for the construction of transition matrices, which map the probabilities of transitions between different stages in the consumer journey. These matrices give marketers clear insight into the most common paths consumers take. In decision tree or regression models, building such a representation can be more complicated, as these models are typically not designed to show a continuous sequence of transitions.

Optimization of Resource Allocation

With an understanding of each transition’s probabilities, Markov Chains allow marketers to allocate resources more precisely. For example, marketers can focus campaigns on specific stages with low transition probabilities to increase conversions. Other models, such as decision trees, typically produce broader, less specific recommendations regarding key transition points in the customer journey.

Dynamic Evaluation of Campaign Effectiveness

Markov Chains enable dynamic evaluation of campaign effectiveness by examining how each campaign impacts transitions between stages. In logistic regression or decision tree models, evaluations typically focus only on the final outcome (e.g., whether a purchase was made) without

addressing the campaign's influence on intermediate stages. Overall, Markov Chains are superior in consumer behavior analysis due to their ability to measure transition probabilities between stages, map the consumer journey sequentially, and provide insights that can be used to optimize marketing strategies at each stage. This makes Markov Chains especially relevant and suitable for analyzing consumer journeys that involve a specific sequence of stages in the purchase decision-making process.

Using Markov Chains in consumer behavior analysis presents several limitations and challenges that are important to consider, including the memoryless property, limitations of transition data, difficulty in handling dynamic consumer behavior, constraints in modeling non-linear paths, challenges in interpreting multi-channel cases, and issues with handling very large data volumes.

Memoryless Property

One of the basic properties of Markov Chains is the memoryless property, meaning that the future state depends only on the current state and does not consider previous transition history. This property may not always be suitable in the context of complex consumer behavior, where purchase decisions are often influenced by prior interactions or experiences from earlier stages. For example, a consumer who has experienced several negative interactions may be less likely to proceed to the purchase stage, but the Markov Chain model is unable to capture this pattern because it does not consider transition history.

Limitations of Transition Data

To build an accurate Markov Chain model, complete transition data is needed, covering every possible transition between stages in the consumer journey. However, in practice, transition data is often incomplete or unavailable, especially if there are stages or interaction channels that have not been recorded or monitored. These limitations can reduce the model's accuracy and restrict analysis, meaning that prediction results may not fully reflect actual consumer behavior. Consumer behavior often changes over time, influenced by factors such as market trends, shifts in preferences, or other external forces. Traditional Markov Chains assume that transition probabilities remain constant over time, making it difficult to capture dynamic changes in consumer behavior. To address this, the model needs continuous updating or adjustment with new data, which can require additional resources.

Limitations in Modeling Non-Linear Paths

Markov Chains work well in models with a relatively linear sequence of stages. However, consumer journeys are often non-linear in practice, where consumers may return to previous stages or jump between stages in no clear order. This makes it challenging to use Markov Chain models, as extensions can become very complex and require much larger transition matrices.

Difficulty in Interpretation for Multi-Channel Cases

In multi-channel cases, such as consumer interactions involving social media, email, applications, and websites, it is difficult to integrate all channels into a single Markov Chain model because each channel may have different transition characteristics. Integration between channels requires complex and sometimes difficult-to-interpret transition matrices, complicating decision-making.

Limitations in Handling Very Large Data Volumes

When user data volume is very large, such as on platforms with millions of users, building and processing an accurate transition matrix becomes highly challenging. This process requires substantial computing resources and may demand sophisticated optimization techniques. Without supporting technology, such analysis can be time-consuming and may hinder the implementation of Markov Chain-based marketing strategies.

Considering these limitations, it is important for marketers to understand that Markov Chains are just one tool for analyzing consumer behavior and may need to be combined with other approaches or more complex models to provide more accurate and relevant results according to business needs.

Building a Markov Chain model to analyze consumer behaviour requires a technical implementation, including collecting data, building a transition matrix, validating the model, analyzing results and interpretations, and optimizing strategies based on findings.

- **Collecting Data**

1. **Identify Stages (States):** Determine the stages in the consumer journey, such as awareness, interest, consideration, purchase, and loyalty.
2. **Collect Historical Data:** Gather consumer interaction data at each stage. This data can come from various channels, such as websites, applications, emails, and social media. Ensure the data includes the time or sequence of transitions between stages for each consumer.
3. **Clean and Format Data:** Perform data cleaning to remove irrelevant information and format the data to suit the requirements of the Markov Chain model, including adding labels or IDs for each stage.

- **Building a Transition Matrix**

1. **Identify Transitions:** List all possible transitions between stages, such as from awareness to interest, interest to consideration, and so forth.
2. **Calculate Transition Frequency:** Count the actual number of transitions between each pair of stages. For example, calculate how many times consumers move from the awareness stage to the interest stage based on historical data.
3. **Normalize Data to Get Transition Probabilities:** Convert transition frequencies to probabilities by dividing the number of transitions from one stage to another by the total number of transitions out of the initial stage. The result is a transition matrix showing the probability of each transition between stages.

- **Validate the Model**

1. **Test the Consistency of the Transition Matrix:** Ensure that each row in the transition matrix adds up to 1 (100%), as this is a basic requirement in the Markov Chain model.
2. **Split Data for Validation:** Divide the data into two parts: training data and testing data. Use the training data to build the transition matrix and the testing data to validate the model's accuracy in predicting transitions.
3. **Error Analysis:** Evaluate the model's predictions against the testing data and conduct error analysis to understand how accurately the model captures actual transition patterns.

- **Analyze Results and Interpretation**

1. **Predict Consumer Behavior Patterns:** Use the transition matrix to analyze the most common paths taken by consumers. Identify stages with high or low transition probabilities to understand where consumers tend to drop off or continue their journey.
2. **Identify Bottlenecks in the Consumer Journey:** Analyze the transition matrix to find stages with low transition probabilities to the next stage. These points can be targeted for marketing or promotional interventions.

3. Simulate and Predict Future Behavior: Based on the transition matrix, simulate the consumer journey over a certain period to predict future consumer behavior and estimate conversions at each stage.

- Optimize Strategy Based on Findings

1. Campaign Targeting and Personalization: Create targeted campaign strategies for stages with low transition probabilities based on the analysis. For instance, offer special promotions to consumers in the consideration stage to increase the likelihood of purchase.

2. Budget Allocation Based on Channel Effectiveness: Use transition matrix data to identify the most effective channels for moving consumers between stages. Allocate the marketing budget to channels with the greatest impact on the consumer journey.

3. Continuous Evaluation and Model Updates: Periodically update the transition matrix with new data to ensure the model remains relevant to dynamic consumer behavior. Regularly evaluate and optimize the model to improve prediction accuracy and marketing strategy effectiveness.

These steps will help build an effective Markov Chain model for analyzing the consumer journey, enabling marketers to make data-driven decisions in their marketing strategies.

The potential for using Markov Chains in the future is very promising, especially when integrated with machine learning (ML) or artificial intelligence (AI) to improve the accuracy of consumer behavior predictions. Some potential applications are as follows:

- Combination with Machine Learning to Improve Prediction Accuracy By combining Markov Chains and machine learning algorithms, companies can dynamically update the transition matrix based on the latest data. Machine learning algorithms can detect changes in consumer behavior patterns and update transition probabilities in real time. For example, machine learning models can recognize patterns that indicate a tendency for consumers to move to a certain stage after a specific action, thereby enhancing the accuracy of Markov Chain predictions.

- Integration with Deep Learning to Capture More Complex Patterns Integration with deep learning techniques, such as neural networks, can help identify more complex behavioral patterns that traditional Markov Chain models cannot capture. Neural networks can uncover hidden factors in consumer behavior data, which can then be fed into the Markov Chain model to account for additional context or influencing factors in the prediction, allowing for richer and more accurate behavior modeling.

- Hybrid Model Development for Dynamic Consumer Behavior

In a dynamic market environment, consumer behavior can change rapidly. By integrating Markov Chains with other AI-based predictive models, such as clustering models or time-series forecasting, companies can manage behavioral changes more adaptively. This hybrid model enables companies to recognize shifting trends and make rapid adjustments, such as automatically modifying marketing strategies or personalization approaches.

- Real-Time Personalization of User Experience

With the help of AI, Markov Chains can be used to personalize user experiences in real time. AI models trained with historical behavioral data can predict the next stage of the consumer journey, while Markov Chains assign probabilities to each stage. With this combination, companies can present the most relevant content, offers, or promotions to users at each interaction point in real time, thereby enhancing the user experience and conversion rates.

- Application in Smarter Recommendation Systems

The integration of Markov Chains and machine learning can be applied in smarter recommendation systems. For instance, Markov Chains can predict the stages of a consumer journey, while ML-based recommendation algorithms can provide the most suitable products or services at each stage. This makes the recommendation system more responsive and relevant, as it is based on a deeper understanding of the consumer journey.

- Automation and Optimization of Marketing Strategies with AI

With the integration of Markov Chains and AI, marketing strategies can be automated and optimized based on consumer behavior data. AI can manage and update the transition matrix automatically and make decisions on marketing strategies based on the most effective transition probabilities. Additionally, AI can identify critical points in the consumer journey where intervention is needed, allowing marketing strategies to be adjusted quickly and efficiently.

- Continuous Campaign Monitoring and Evaluation

With the help of AI, Markov Chains can be used to continuously monitor and evaluate marketing campaigns. For example, AI algorithms can identify changes in transition patterns caused by new campaigns and make adjustments to the Markov Chain model according to the effectiveness of the campaign. This enables companies to evaluate campaigns more accurately and adjust strategies based on real-time results.

By combining Markov Chains with AI technology, companies can create more adaptive and predictive models that better respond to changes in consumer behavior. This integration allows for higher personalization, more efficient campaign optimization, and overall improvement in the consumer experience, making it a highly promising strategy for the future.

The fundamental equation in a Markov Chain is the transition probability equation, which describes the likelihood of moving from one state to another in a system based on a transition matrix. Here are some key mathematical equations used in the Markov Chain model:

1. Transition Matrix

The transition matrix P is a matrix containing the transition probabilities between states in the system. If there are n states, then the transition matrix P has dimensions $n \times n$ and can be expressed as follows:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{11} & P_{21} & \dots & P_{n1} & P_{12} & P_{22} & \dots & P_{n2} & \dots & \dots & P_{1n} & P_{2n} & \dots & P_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, p_{ij} represents the probability of transitioning from state i to state j , with the requirement that each row in the matrix sums to 1:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n p_{ij} = 1$$

2. State Probability Equation

If we have an initial state probability vector $\pi^{(0)}$, which shows the initial probability distribution across all states, then the probability distribution after one step (or one time interval) can be represented as:

$$\pi^{(1)} = \pi^{(0)} P$$

where $\pi^{(1)}$ is the state probability vector after one step. More generally, for k steps ahead, the probability distribution can be determined as:

$$\pi^{(k)} = \pi^{(0)} P^k$$

3. Steady-State Distribution

In many cases, a Markov Chain will reach a steady-state distribution (or equilibrium state) after a long period, where the probabilities for each state remain constant. The steady-state distribution π satisfies the following equation:

$$\pi = \pi P$$

In other words, π is a probability vector that remains the same after applying the transition matrix P . To satisfy the distribution requirement, the elements of π must sum to 1:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i = 1$$

4. Expected Return Time

Markov Chains can also be used to calculate the expected return time to a particular state. If we want to calculate the expected return time to state i , we can use the following equation (for positive recurrent chains):

$$E[T_i] = \frac{1}{\pi_i}$$

Where $E[T_i]$ is the average time to return to state i , and π_i is the steady-state probability of state i .

These equations form the basis of the Markov Chain model and are used to analyze and predict system behavior based on transition probabilities between states.

In the digital era, economic activities such as buying and selling have become much simpler than in the past. Online shopping is one of the most prominent examples of this shift. The growing popularity of online shopping is closely tied to technological advances that have transformed or even replaced certain traditional practices. As a result, online shopping has become a lifestyle for many people. With the rapid growth of the internet, numerous activities, including shopping, are now conducted more instantly and efficiently. The boom in online shopping is fueled by consumer preferences for ease, affordability, and convenience. The rise of online shopping is especially noteworthy in the digital age, where increasingly sophisticated technology makes online shopping more appealing to many people. Even during the current pandemic, online shopping has grown in

popularity as it allows people to stay safely at home. While some people still prefer to shop in physical stores, many choose online shopping to avoid crowds and reduce risks associated with in-person shopping. In addition, online shopping eliminates the need to visit physical stores or markets; a simple tap on a device or mobile phone can enable consumers to purchase and receive desired items. In today's digital age, almost everyone has multiple online shopping apps, finding them useful for saving time. The convenience of payment processing through bank transfers or even supermarket services further contributes to the efficiency of online shopping, making it increasingly popular and seen as a time-saving, effective alternative.

According to Kalakota and Whiston, e-commerce is defined as online shopping conducted over the internet, with transactions completed through digital money transfers. They define e-commerce from four perspectives:

- **Communication Perspective.** E-commerce is a process of delivering goods, services, information, or payments via computers or other electronic devices.
- **Business Process Perspective.** E-commerce is an application of technology for the automation of business transactions and workflow.

In a broad sense, e-commerce is the use of computer networks to improve organizational performance, increase profitability, gain market share, enhance customer service, and expedite product delivery. E-commerce involves more than ordering goods from an online catalog; it encompasses all aspects of an organization's electronic interactions with stakeholders, the people who shape the future of the organization. E-commerce leverages information technology infrastructure and the internet, which play essential roles in business today. In the current information era, many offline companies are actively developing internet technology to enhance their operations. Zwaas defines e-commerce as a tool for sharing business information, maintaining business relationships, and conducting transactions via communication media. At its core, e-commerce is conducting business online. In its simplest form, e-commerce involves selling products to consumers over the internet; however, any business activity conducted electronically qualifies as e-commerce. In brief, e-commerce is the creation, management, and expansion of commercial relationships online.

Consumer behavior studies how individuals, groups, or organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants. Consumer behavior is influenced by various factors, including psychological, social and personal factors.

Psychological Factors:

- **Motivation:** The drive that makes consumers interested in buying.
- **Perception:** How consumers interpret information and make decisions.
- **Attitude:** Consumers' views of a particular product or brand.
- **Learning:** Past experiences that influence future decisions.

Social Factors:

- **Family:** The influence of family members on purchasing decisions.
- **Reference Groups:** The influence of friends, colleagues, or communities on purchasing.
- **Social Status:** A person's social position, which can influence product or service choices.

Personal Factors:

- **Age and Life Stage:** Product preferences change with age.

- Occupation: The type of employment influences consumption patterns.
- Economic Conditions: Income and savings impact purchasing power

There are several connections between marketing concepts and values taught in the Qur'an, particularly in terms of ethics, honesty, and consumer interactions. Below are some key areas of alignment:

1. Honesty and Transparency in Transactions

The Qur'an emphasizes the importance of honesty and transparency in all forms of trade and transactions. In Surah Al-Mutaffifin (83:1-3), Allah warns against those who cheat in weights and measures:

وَيْلٌ لِّلْمُطَفِّفِينَ
 ۝۱ الَّذِينَ إِذَا اكْتَالُوا عَلَى النَّاسِ يَسْتَوْفُونَ
 ۝۲ وَإِذَا كَالُوا لَهُمْ أَوْ وَزَنُوا لَهُمْ يُخْسِرُونَ

“Woe to the cheaters, who, when they take a measure from others, take it in full, and when they measure or weigh it for others, they give less.”

In the context of marketing, this verse teaches the importance of providing honest information about products, quality, prices, and services. Marketers are expected to uphold transparency with consumers and avoid providing misleading or exaggerated information.

2. Prioritizing Consumer Needs and Satisfaction

Islam considers serving others with kindness and helping to meet their needs as acts of worship. This principle is highlighted in Surah Al-Ma'un (107:1-3), where Allah reminds of the importance of caring for those in need:

۝۱ أَرَأَيْتَ الَّذِي يُكَذِّبُ بِالدِّينِ
 ۝۲ ۗذَٰلِكَ الَّذِي يُدْعُ النَّبِيَّ
 ۝۳ ۗوَلَا يُخِضُّ عَلَىٰ طَعَامِ الْمَسْكِينِ

“Do you know who denies the religion? He is the one who rebukes the orphan and does not encourage the feeding of the poor.”

In marketing, this principle can be interpreted as a responsibility to understand consumer needs and provide products or services that are truly beneficial. Ethical marketing, according to Islamic values, aims to deliver meaningful value to consumers beyond simply pursuing profit.

3. Competing in an Ethical Manner

The Qur'an encourages humans to compete in goodness, a principle known as *fastabiqul kbairat*. In Surah Al-Baqarah (2:148), Allah says:

وَلِكُلِّ وِجْهَةٌ هُوَ مُوَلِّبُهَا فَاسْتَبِقُوا الخَيْرَاتِ ۚ إِنَّ مَا تَكُونُوا يَأْتِ بِكُمْ اللهُ جَمِيعًا ۗ إِنَّ اللهَ عَلَىٰ شَيْءٍ قَدِيرٌ

“So compete in goodness. Wherever you are, Allah will gather you all together (on the Day of Resurrection).”

In marketing, this principle implies that competition should be conducted in an ethical and respectful manner. Marketers are encouraged to avoid harmful methods toward competitors or consumers, such as negative campaigns, manipulation, or defamation.

4. Fairness in Pricing

The Qur'an emphasizes justice in all aspects of life, including in setting prices. In Surah An-Nisa (4:29), Allah reminds:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَأْكُلُوا أَمْوَالَكُم بَيْنَكُم بِالْبَاطِلِ إِلَّا أَنْ تَكُونَ تِجَارَةً عَنْ تَرَاضٍ مِنْكُمْ وَلَا تَقْتُلُوا أَنْفُسَكُمْ إِنَّ اللَّهَ كَانَ بِكُمْ رَحِيمًا
“O you who believe, do not consume each other's wealth in a false way, except by means of commerce that is mutually agreed upon among you.”

This verse advocates for fair pricing, ensuring that neither the buyer nor the seller is harmed. Marketers are encouraged to avoid exploitative practices and set prices that reflect a fair balance between profit and value.

5. Ethics in Promotional Communication

Islam places great importance on honest and respectful communication. The Qur'an advises believers to speak truthfully and kindly, as in Surah Al-Ahzab (33:70):

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اتَّقُوا اللَّهَ وَقُولُوا قَوْلًا سَدِيدًا
“O you who believe, fear Allah and speak the truth.”

In marketing, this can translate to honest and transparent promotional communication. Marketers are advised to avoid deceptive language and exaggeration when promoting their products or services.

6. Trustworthiness in Fulfilling Duties and Responsibilities

The concept of trust, or *amanah*, is a fundamental value in Islam and is relevant in marketing as well. In Surah Al-Anfal (8:27), Allah says:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا لَا تَخُونُوا اللَّهَ وَالرَّسُولَ وَتَخُونُوا أَمْنِكُمْ وَأَنْتُمْ تَعْلَمُونَ
“O you who believe, do not betray Allah and His Messenger, and do not betray the trusts that have been entrusted to you, while you know (the consequences).”

In business and marketing, trust implies honoring the commitments made to consumers. Marketers are expected to uphold their responsibilities with integrity and maintain consumer trust in the products or services offered.

Qur'anic teachings on honesty, justice, and ethics in social interactions (*muamalah*) are highly relevant to the field of marketing. Islamic-based marketing principles emphasize not only profit but also the welfare of consumers and fair, ethical competition. Such an approach helps foster long-term, trust-based relationships with consumers and contributes positively to society.

Journal article, in 2016, *Analysis of Loyalty and Research on Loop Brand Development Strategy at PT. Telkomsel Surabaya Branch*, Indira used the Markov Chain model to analyze brand-switching patterns and predict market share in equilibrium conditions. Her findings indicate that LOOP's market share in equilibrium is estimated to reach 35.7% within 7.5 years. She suggests that the Markov Chain analysis method, which has not been widely applied in this context, provides a new perspective for developing marketing strategies.

Similarly, in 2017, Ilham Pratama and Iwan Krinadi conducted a study titled *Analysis of E-Commerce Store Customer Data using Markov Chain*, focusing on consumer behavior in e-commerce. Their results indicate that Lazada, Tokopedia, and Bukalapak are among the most frequently visited platforms. The Markov model proved effective in accurately predicting customer movements. They also noted a significant increase in e-commerce sales trends in Indonesia, with sales projected to reach 10.9 billion USD in 2017. However, their study highlights a limitation: the inability of the model to account for external factors, such as market trends, promotions, and technological changes, which

can influence customer behavior. They recommend further development of the model across other e-commerce platforms to ensure its validity and generalizability.

In another study from 2017, *Marketing Strategy Through Markov Optimization to Predict Sales in Specific Periods*, Husni Muharram Ritonga, Andysah Putera Utama Siahaan, and Suginam investigated the Markov Chain's capacity to understand market dynamics and forecast potential customer acquisition. They found that while the Markov Chain is useful for market analysis, it has limitations in reflecting real-world conditions, as it assumes transition probabilities remain constant over time despite fluctuating market conditions. They suggest further research to include additional variables that influence consumer behavior and purchase decisions and to assess the impact of dynamic marketing strategies.

In a 2021 study titled *Research on Marketing Prediction Model Based on Markov Prediction*, Haiying Chen, Haiyan Chen, Wei Zhang, Chaodan Yang, and Hongxiu Cui demonstrated that Markov Chains could provide accurate predictions for sales and customer behavior, especially when using wavelet-reconstructed data as opposed to original data. They noted that Markov Chains are effective in capturing dynamic trends in market conditions over time, enhancing their applicability in marketing scenarios. By analyzing customer transitions, the model helps businesses better understand customer loyalty and retention, offering actionable insights for marketing strategies. However, the study acknowledges the need for further research to address the limitations of the Markov framework, such as the influence of external factors like economic changes and competitor actions. Additionally, the authors recommend exploring Markov model applications across various industry sectors to validate its versatility and robustness. A key limitation identified in this study is that the Markov model is most effective for short- and medium-term predictions, while its use for long-term forecasting remains uncertain and requires additional investigation.

The research title *Proposal of Markov Chain to Determine Buying Probability in Period, With Non-Determined Probability Factors to Elucidated Consumer Behavior* researched by Hector D., Molina Ruiz, Stephani M., Rojano Chavez shows that the Markov Chain approach can effectively predict purchase probability and market share among competing brands. The suggestion from this research is that the implications for volatile markets can be explored thoroughly. In the future, it can discuss how to mitigate problems arising from incomplete or biased data. Research with Markov Chains can be expanded with other variables such as economic changes, competitor actions, or technological advances. Mahreen Nasir and C. I. Ezeife in their research entitled *Semantic Enhanced Markov Model for Sequential E-Commerce Product Recommendation* recommend that the Semantic Enhanced Markov Model (SEMMRec) shows increased accuracy in predicting the next component recommendation compared to the traditional model. The integration of semantic knowledge significantly overcomes the problems of limitations and ambiguous predictions in traditional Markov models. In terms of customer satisfaction, the Markov model provides personalized and semantically rich recommendations that enhance customer satisfaction and engagement. The limitations of this study are the high complexity due to the increasing number of states in the Markov model, which complicates the calculation and causes overfitting. Existing methods often produce ambiguous predictions when several components have similar transition probabilities from the current state. Many models do not incorporate semantic relationships derived from product metadata or user interactions, limiting their effectiveness in understanding user preferences.

Markov Chain Analysis to Predict Consumer Switching on the Manado-Jakarta Route conducted by Fatimah N., Yohanes A., R. Langi, and Charles Mongi shows that Markov Chain analysis successfully predicts consumer movement on airlines operating on the Manado-Jakarta route. The suggestion from this study is the need for more in-depth research on the fundamental factors that influence consumer preferences and behavior towards airline selection. In addition, it is necessary

to explore broader factors such as pricing strategies, customer satisfaction, and brand loyalty, as well as incorporate longitudinal studies to evaluate changes in consumer preferences over a long period of time.

Analysis of Brand Switching and Marketing Strategy Using Markov Chain and Game Theory in Medan City conducted by Rendy Ihsan Halim and Pardomuan Sitompul in 2024 showed that the probability of customer switching can be measured using the Markov Chain approach. The suggestion from this study is the need for a deeper study of marketing strategies on brand switching patterns that have not been widely studied using the approach of both methods. In addition, there is a lack of comprehensive analysis of customer behavior in brand switching and determining optimal strategies using Markov Chain and Game Theory.

Analysis of Investment Results Using Markov Chain Random Walk in 2024 shows that the Mexican market performed better than other markets during the study period, while India performed poorly. These findings provide important information for market regulators and investors in setting regulations and making investment decisions. The proposal from this study is the use of Markov Chain random Walk to analyze investment results that combine the assumption of randomness from random walk with the probabilistic structure of Markov Chain.

Markov chain analysis to predict natural disasters in the Bangka Belitung Islands Province as part of preventive efforts to prevent environmental damage in 2023 shows that floods and forest fires are the most frequent disasters. This study also provides statistical data on the probability of various disasters in 2023. The prediction accuracy is evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Square Error (MSE), with values of 0.356 and 0.17, respectively. This study highlights the effectiveness of the Markov Chain method in predicting natural disasters based on historical data.

The study on Markov Energy Efficiency of Ships conducted by Garbatov, et al., showed that the transition between different CII levels in survey data was used to estimate the probability of the analyzed ship transition between different CII grates. Different transition matrices using increasingly stringent CII laws were also used and analyzed and fed into a risk-based model that uses CII rates as input to determine the most appropriate ship energy efficiency management plan.

In their research titled *Proposal of Markov Chain to Determine Buying Probability in Period, With Non-Determined Probability Factors to Elucidate Consumer Behavior*, Hector D., Molina Ruiz, and Stephani M., Rojano Chavez demonstrate that the Markov Chain approach can effectively predict purchase probability and market share among competing brands. They suggest that the implications for volatile markets could be further explored. Future research could also address issues arising from incomplete or biased data. Expanding Markov Chain research to include additional variables such as economic changes, competitor actions, or technological advancements is recommended.

Similarly, Mahreen Nasir and C. I. Ezeife, in their study *Semantic Enhanced Markov Model for Sequential E-Commerce Product Recommendation*, show that the Semantic Enhanced Markov Model (SEMMRec) increases accuracy in predicting sequential product recommendations compared to traditional models. Integrating semantic knowledge helps address limitations and ambiguity issues commonly found in traditional Markov models. This approach provides more personalized, semantically rich recommendations that enhance customer satisfaction and engagement. However, they note the model's limitations, such as high complexity and potential overfitting due to an increasing number of states. Additionally, existing methods often generate ambiguous predictions when multiple components have similar transition probabilities, as many models lack semantic relationships from product metadata or user interactions.

In their study *Markov Chain Analysis to Predict Consumer Switching on the Manado-Jakarta Route*, Fatimah N., Yohanes A., R. Langi, and Charles Mongi successfully applied Markov Chain analysis to predict consumer movements among airlines operating on the Manado-Jakarta route. They recommend

further research on fundamental factors influencing consumer preferences and behavior in airline selection. Additionally, they suggest examining broader factors, such as pricing strategies, customer satisfaction, and brand loyalty, as well as incorporating longitudinal studies to evaluate changes in consumer preferences over time.

In *Analysis of Brand Switching and Marketing Strategy Using Markov Chain and Game Theory in Medan City*, Rendy Ihsan Halim and Pardomuan Sitompul (2024) found that customer switching probabilities can be effectively measured using the Markov Chain approach. They recommend a more in-depth study of marketing strategies in brand switching patterns, which have not been extensively explored using both Markov Chain and Game Theory methods. A comprehensive analysis of customer behavior in brand switching and determining optimal strategies through these methods is needed.

The 2024 study *Analysis of Investment Results Using Markov Chain Random Walk* reports that the Mexican market outperformed other markets during the study period, while the Indian market underperformed. These findings provide valuable insights for market regulators and investors in creating regulations and making investment decisions. The study suggests that the Markov Chain Random Walk approach, which combines the randomness assumption of a random walk with the probabilistic structure of Markov Chains, could be an effective tool for investment analysis.

In the 2023 study *Markov Chain Analysis to Predict Natural Disasters in the Bangka Belitung Islands Province as Part of Preventive Efforts to Prevent Environmental Damage*, it was found that floods and forest fires are the most frequent disasters in the region. The study provides statistical probabilities for various natural disasters in 2023, with prediction accuracy evaluated using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Square Error (MSE) values of 0.356 and 0.17, respectively. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the Markov Chain method for predicting natural disasters based on historical data.

Markov Energy Efficiency of Ships, Garbatov et al. examined the transition probabilities between different CII levels in survey data to estimate ship transitions across various CII grades. Transition matrices reflecting increasingly stringent CII regulations were analyzed and integrated into a risk-based model, which uses CII ratings as inputs to determine optimal ship energy efficiency management plans.

The study titled *Applied Research Analysis of Game Theory and Markov Chain* concludes that Markov Chains and Game Theory serve as highly influential theoretical foundations across numerous industries and fields. These theories have gradually promoted the application of mathematical models to advance societal, scientific, and technological development. By analyzing and utilizing the integration, steady-state properties, periodicity, and ergodicity of Markov Chains, this research applies these concepts to signal transmission, traffic management, and bank bad debt analysis. Markov Chains are effectively used to model various transmission processes, facilitating applications in these fields.

In *Analysis of Urban Sprawl Dynamics Using Machine Learning, CA-Markov Chain, and the Shannon Entropy Model: A Case Study in Mbombela City, South Africa*, findings indicate a significant increase in urbanization, accompanied by rapid land use changes. Using the CA-Markov Chain model, the study predicts that urban areas will continue to expand rapidly. The study's long-term predictions, which integrate machine learning and specialized modeling, suggest that without planned intervention, the urban sprawl pattern is likely to persist.

In their 2021 study, *Markov Chain Analysis in Brand Loyalty and Brand Switching*, Ade Sitoresmi Phasa and Yuliani Puji Astuti demonstrate the effectiveness of Markov Chain analysis in predicting customer behavior related to brand loyalty and switching. Their findings reveal that services from Bank B are the most utilized, followed by Bank A, Bank D, and Bank C, respectively.

In *Markov Chain in Determining Market Share and Equilibrium: Case Study of Cilok Traders in Alun-Alun Pemalang Regency* (2021), Endro Tri Susdarwono used Markov Chain analysis to calculate market share among four types of “cilok” vendors (cilok A, B, C, and D). For the second period, market shares were projected at 21.5%, 28%, 24%, and 26.5%, respectively. In the third period, market shares were estimated at 21.8% for cilok A, 27.3% for cilok B, 24% for cilok C, and 26.8% for cilok D. Equilibrium market share was calculated at 21.7% for cilok A, 25.8% for cilok B, 23.9% for cilok C, and 28.6% for cilok D.

In the study titled *Application of Markov Chains in Analyzing Shopping Place Changes: A Case Study of STIMLOG Students Who Shop at Alfamart, Indomaret, and Yomart*, it was found that customers, particularly at Indomaret, show a strong tendency to continue shopping at the same location. The POM QM tool showed varying probabilities for customer shifts, which could be attributed to differences in calculation methods or model assumptions. Alfamart is advised to address its gradual decline in market share, while Indomaret has seen an increase in visitor numbers. Yomart maintains a stable, albeit smaller, customer base compared to its competitors.

The *Analysis of Factors Influencing Online Purchasing Decisions in the Shopee Marketplace in 2024* identifies four variables - Online Customer Rating, Online Customer Review, Price, and Free Shipping - as having a significant impact on online purchasing decisions, both individually and collectively. These factors account for 89.5% of the influence on purchasing decisions, with Online Customer Rating having the greatest impact, followed by Online Customer Review, Free Shipping, and Price.

The study by Erico Alfayed, Lista Ramadeli, Raket Agnestasia, Viona Amalina, Zhatil Hanani Octavia Swid, and Hendra Riofita, titled *Analysis of E-Commerce Marketing and Sales Strategies on TikTok Shop* (2023), employs a descriptive qualitative approach using content and deductive analysis to explore marketing and sales strategies on TikTok Shop within the e-commerce context. The results show that TikTok Shop offers a convenient shopping experience through various features designed for sellers, creators, and affiliates. Additionally, a strategic partnership with Tokopedia aims to expand market reach and empower MSMEs. TikTok Shop utilizes diverse advertising formats to boost sales. However, the study highlights areas for improvement, particularly in the payment system and customer response. It suggests further research to compare TikTok Shop's marketing strategies with those of other e-commerce platforms.

In their research titled *Application of Markov Chain Analysis to Predict Patient Status at the Buton Regency General Hospital (RSUD)*, Siti Nuryam, Arman, Norma Muhtar, Jufra, and La Gubu applied Markov Chain analysis to predict patient status changes using secondary data from the Medical Research Unit of Buton District Hospital in 2021. The study transformed patient status data into a transition probability matrix to predict changes in patient status. Results indicate that the Markov Chain model effectively illustrates the probability of patient status transitions and identifies steady-state probabilities. The study emphasizes the importance of expanding the number of states and suggests further research to enhance the accuracy and relevance of the analysis for hospital service planning and management.

A study by M. Muharam, P. Wibowo, R. Supriatna, and A. S. Maulana, entitled *Markov Chain Analysis to Predict Online Motorcycle Taxi Drivers Operating in the Gojek Cery Community*, utilized the Markov Chain method with data collected through direct observation within the Gojek Cery community over two days. Findings show the probability of online motorcycle taxi drivers' activity on the third day based on their activity on the first day. Results reveal that if a driver is active on the first day, the probability of operating on the third day is 63.5%. Conversely, if inactive on the first day, the probability of returning to operation on the third day is 56.3%. The study notes limitations, particularly the exclusion of external factors such as demand fluctuations or regulatory

changes that may affect driver behavior. Additionally, the model's reliance on historical data may not fully capture dynamic shifts in driver behavior.

Anang Asyrofi, Indira Anggriani, and Annisa Rahmita Soemarsono's study, *Application of Discrete Time Markov Chain Method in Estimating Smartphone Brand Usage Switching in Balikpapan*, aims to analyze consumer switching behavior among smartphone brands using the discrete-time Markov Chain method. Data were collected via questionnaires targeting smartphone users in Balikpapan. The analysis process included descriptive statistics, data plotting, classification, and the construction of a switching pattern table and transition probability matrix to predict each brand's market share. Findings reveal that the highest brand switching occurs from Apple to Samsung, with Apple maintaining the largest market share in 2022. Brands such as Oppo, Realme, and Vivo are predicted to increase in market share, whereas Apple and Samsung may experience a decline. The study acknowledges limitations in accounting for market saturation effects, where consumer loyalty is not fully incorporated into the Markov Chain model, suggesting that future research consider factors influencing long-term consumer loyalty.

Discussion

The research papers reviewed demonstrate that the Markov Chain model and its related analytical approaches are highly effective in analyzing and predicting customer behavior and market dynamics across various sectors, including e-commerce, aviation, and other industries. Findings indicate that this method effectively maps consumer behavior patterns and provides valuable insights for developing more targeted and effective marketing strategies. The Markov Chain model can identify consumer preferences and predict transition probabilities between choices in competitive market conditions. Its advantage lies in its ability to generate insights from relatively simple historical data, although it has limitations in accounting for external factors and sudden, drastic changes in consumer behavior.

This study examines the use of the Markov Chain model for sales prediction in the context of digitalized marketing within e-commerce. Based on the reviewed literature, the Markov Chain model effectively supports the mapping of customer behavior and consumer preferences in dynamic market environments. The analysis indicates that the Markov Chain model can map consumer behavior patterns and predict transitions between choices, providing valuable insights for the development of more accurate marketing strategies.

However, it should be acknowledged that the Markov Chain model has limitations in accounting for external factors, such as market trends or sudden shifts in customer behavior, which may impact prediction accuracy. Therefore, this approach should be supplemented with additional data or external variables, such as customer loyalty and satisfaction metrics, to better reflect realistic conditions.

This study also highlights the importance of digitalization in expanding market reach and enhancing the effectiveness of marketing campaigns. Digital technology allows marketers to adapt strategies to specific customer segments more easily. However, it is crucial to evaluate these strategies periodically to ensure they remain aligned with evolving consumer preferences.

The advantages of using Markov Chains in E-Commerce marketing are sequential transition modelling, resource allocation optimization, dynamic campaign evaluation, data-driven personalization. Markov Chains are effective in modeling consumer journeys as they move through stages, such as awareness, consideration, and purchase. This sequential structure helps marketers identify the most critical touchpoints and high-churn stages. By understanding probabilities at each stage, marketers can allocate resources more effectively, focusing on channels or stages with higher

conversion probabilities. Markov Chains enable real-time assessment of campaign impact by analyzing how transitions shift due to marketing efforts. This approach supports more responsive adjustments to campaigns. The model allows for personalization by segmenting users based on transition probabilities, which is particularly useful for targeting promotions and reducing churn.

The disadvantages and limitations of using Markov Chain in E-Commerce are memoryless property, static transition probabilities, difficulty with non-linear consumer journeys, handling multi-channel interaction, and high data requirements. One of the inherent limitations of Markov Chains is their memoryless nature, meaning future states depend only on the current state, not past interactions. This can overlook complex consumer behavior influenced by cumulative experiences. Markov Chains assume constant transition probabilities over time, which may not capture the dynamic nature of consumer behavior. Updates and recalibration of the model are necessary to maintain relevance. Real-world consumer journeys are often non-linear, with users moving back and forth between stages. Expanding Markov Chains to accommodate such paths can complicate the model. Integrating different marketing channels (e.g., social media, email, website) into a single Markov Chain model is complex, as each channel may require unique transition matrices. Accurate transition matrices require extensive historical data across various stages and channels, which can be challenging to obtain and manage, especially in real-time applications.

The integration of Markov Chains with advanced technologies, such as Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), could enhance predictive accuracy and address some of the model's limitations. Potential advancements include:

1. **Machine Learning Integration for Dynamic Updates:** By combining Markov Chains with ML algorithms, transition probabilities can be updated continuously based on recent consumer data, allowing the model to adapt to changing behavior patterns.
2. **Deep Learning for Complex Patterns:** Neural networks can capture complex relationships and latent factors influencing consumer behavior, providing a richer context for Markov Chain predictions.
3. **Real-Time Personalization:** AI-driven real-time personalization, using Markov Chains to anticipate the next steps in the consumer journey, could help companies deliver targeted content and promotions, enhancing the user experience.
4. **Hybrid Modeling for Adaptive Strategies:** Incorporating clustering models or time-series forecasting alongside Markov Chains could allow companies to adapt more effectively to shifting market trends.
5. **Advanced Multi-Channel Attribution:** Future research could focus on creating an integrated Markov model capable of handling multi-channel interactions, providing a holistic view of the consumer journey.

Conclusion

Markov Chains offer valuable insights into consumer behavior in digital marketing, especially for sequential modeling and optimizing conversion paths. However, their limitations highlight the need for periodic recalibration and potential integration with other advanced models. Future advancements combining Markov Chains with AI and ML hold promise for enhancing prediction accuracy, supporting adaptive marketing strategies, and enabling real-time personalization. This approach could become increasingly essential as digital marketing grows more complex and data-driven in the e-commerce sector.

Recommendations

There remain opportunities for future researchers to explore issues that have not been addressed in previous studies, such as integrate machine learning for dynamic transition updates, enhance model complexity with deep learning, expand data collection for multi-channel interactions, implement periodic model recalibration, incorporate real-time personalization features, investigate external factors for comprehensive analysis, explore the use of Markov Chains for long-term forecasting, conduct comparative studies with other e-commerce platforms, etc. These recommendations aim to optimize the use of Markov Chains in e-commerce digital marketing, addressing key limitations while leveraging the model's strengths to enhance predictive accuracy, consumer engagement, and strategic decision-making.

References

- Agyekum, L., Aidoo, E. K., Oko, C., & Dowuona, N. (2024). Analysis of investment results using Markov chain random walk.
- Alfayed, E., Ramadeli, L., Agnestasia, R., Amalina, V., Swid, Z. H. O., & Riofita, H. (2023). *Analysis of e-commerce marketing and sales strategy on TikTok Shop*.
- Andry, J. F. (2015). Implementation of Markov chain application in marketing study of e-commerce customer case database.
- Asyrofi, A., Anggriani, I., & Soemarsono, A. R. (2024). Application of discrete time Markov chain method in estimating smartphone brand switching in Balikpapan.
- Chen, H., Chen, H., Zhang, W., Yang, C., & Cui, H. (2021). Marketing prediction model research based on Markov prediction.
- Dalimunthe, D. Y., Fahria, I., & Wahyuni, D. (2023). Markov chain analysis to predict natural disasters in the Bangka Belitung Islands Province as part of preventive efforts to prevent environmental damage. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Sciences*, 1267(1), 012010. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1267/1/012010>
- Fernandes Andry, J. (2015). Implementation of Markov chain application in marketing studies of e-commerce customer case databases.
- Fitrada, I. (2016). Loyalty analysis and loop brand development strategy research at PT. Telkomsel Surabaya Branch.
- Garbatov, Y., Yalamov, D., & Georgiev, P. (2024). Markov chain analysis of ship energy efficiency. *Energy*, 17(12), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17123018>
- Gifari, F. A., Maulana, M. A., & Maulana, S. (2024). Markov chain analysis to determine consumer switching opportunities for laptop brands among industrial engineering students of Indraprasta PGRI University.
- Halim, R. I. (2024). Analysis of brand switching and marketing strategy using Markov chain and game theory in Medan City.
- Halim, R. I. (2024). Analysis of brand switching and marketing strategy using Markov chain and game theory in Medan City.
- Halim, R. I., & Sitompul, P. (2024). Analysis of brand switching and marketing strategy using Markov chain and game theory in Medan City. *Journal of Mathematics and Natural Sciences Cluster Research*, 3(1), 412–423. <https://doi.org/10.55606/jurrimipa.v3i1.2548>

- Harun, M., & Suseno, A. (2024). Analysis of consumer switching opportunities using the Markov chain method in 3 culinary Baso in Galuh Mas Telukjambe Karawang.
- Langi, Y. A. R., Masuku, F. N., & Mongi, C. (2021). Markov chain analysis to predict airline consumer shifts on the Manado-Jakarta route.
- Masuku, F. N., Langi, Y. A. R., & Mongi, C. (2018). Markov chain analysis to predict airline consumer shifts on the Manado-Jakarta route. *Scientific Science*, 18(2), 1–5.
- Mettle, F. O., Aidoo, E. K., & Dowuona, N. (2024). Investment return analysis using Markov chain random walk.
- Mhangara, P., Gidey, E., & Manjoo, R. (2024). Analysis of urban expansion dynamics using machine learning, CA-Markov chains, and Shannon entropy model: A case study in Mbombela City, South Africa. *Environmental Systems Research*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-024-00348-5>
- Molina-Ruiz, H. D., & Rojano-Chavez, S. M. (2021). Proposed Markov chain to determine purchase probability in period, with unspecified probability factors for explained consumer behavior.
- Muharram, M., Wibowo, P., Supriatna, R., & Maulana, A. S. (2024). Markov chain analysis to predict online motorcycle taxi drivers operating in the Gojek Cery Community.
- Nasir, M., & Ezeife, C. I. (2024). Semantic enhanced Markov model for sequential e-commerce product recommendation.
- Niu, C., & Zhou, H. (2023). Applied research analysis of game theory and Markov chains. *Highlights in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 47, 116–121. <https://doi.org/10.54097/hset.v47i.8173>
- Nuryam, S., Arman, N., Muhtar, J., & La Gubu. (2021). Application of Markov chain analysis to predict patient status at Buton District General Hospital (RSUD).
- Phasa, A. S., & Astuti, Y. P. (2021). Analysis of brand switching behavior using the Markov chain method.
- Pratama, I., & Krinadi, I. (2017). Analysis of e-commerce store customer data using the Markov chain method.
- Ritonga, H. M., Siahaan, A. P. U., & Suginam. (2017). Marketing strategy through Markov optimization to predict sales in a certain period.
- Siahaan, R. F. B., Williny, & Ciamas, E. S. (2021). Markov analysis: Strategy to maintain brand image of superior products of North Sumatra.
- Simunapendi, M. O., Nugraha, A. B., Ramadhan, M. F., Anshari, F. H., & Minda, H. (2024). Application of Markov chain in analyzing shopping place changes (Case study of STIMLOG students who shop at Alfamart, Indomaret, and Yomart).
- Susdarwono, E. T. (2021). Markov chain in determining market share and equilibrium: A case study of Cilok vendors in Pemalang Regency Square. *Journal of Mathematics Education (Kudus)*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.21043/jmtk.v4i1.10160>